

A STUDY OF VALUES AMONG PUPIL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was made to find out whether there is any significant difference between values and gender of pupil teachers in respect of Theoretical value, Economic value, Political value, Social value, Aesthetic value. In the present study, random sampling technique was adopted to select a sample of 250 Pupil teachers in Guru Nanak College of Education Dalewal, Hoshiarpur and 'Students Value Inventory' which was developed and standardized by T. Padmanaban, used for collecting data from pupil teachers. The result revealed that there is no significant difference between values of male and female pupil teachers in respect of Religious value. But there is significant difference between values of male and female pupil teachers in respect of Theoretical, Economic, Political, Social and Aesthetic values.

Keywords : Values, Theoretical value, Economic value, Political value, Social value, Aesthetic value and Religious value, pupil teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Education is as old as the human race. It is never ending process of inner growth and development and its period stretches from cradle to the grave. Education, in real sense, is to humanize-humanity, and to make life progressive, cultured and civilized. It is very important for the progress of individual and society. It is through education that man develops his thinking and reasoning, Problem solving and creativity, intelligence and aptitude, positive sentiments and skills, good values and attitudes. It is through education that he is transformed into human, social, moral and spiritual being. Students are the failure of India. The future of country depends upon the values imparted to them during their student life. In today's or a of competition and survival we observe laxity in moral values. Industrialization has led to the emergence of high life style and raised the standard of living of people. It has made man rich in materialistic sense but deteriorated the ethical fiber in the society. People crave for money, power and pelf. They are ready to jeopardize the interest of other people in pursuit of their selfish gains. Values are extremely important for the overall well-being. Moral values provide a structure for student life. Honesty makes students

respectable. Values are related to those activities which are good, useful and valuable from the educational point of view of education and has already been pointed out that according to Adams it is a bipolar process which has two parts – (1) The teacher and (2) The child. The teacher, in order to mould and modify the behavior of the child employs various strategies and tactics to achieve the desired behavioral change in the child. He performs all these activities, because he thinks them as valuable for the purpose in view. As the teacher provides an environment of utility and value to the child, in the same manner the child participates only in those activities which he considers useful and valuable to him.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam, the former President of India in his book ‘India 2020: A Vision of the New Millennium’ has rightly remarked that “If you are a teacher in whatever capacity, you have a very special role to play because more than anybody else it is you who are shaping the future generation. A teacher has a higher responsibility as compared to other professionals as students look upon the teacher as an embodiment of perfection”.

Thus Teachers play an important role in the nation building by character building of the students. The best and the greatest profession in the world is that of a teacher, because the future of a nation depends upon the type of teachers who shape the future generations. Every teacher plays the most important role in shaping the students as enlightened citizen. Teachers are the source of inspiration for students. The relationship between student and teacher is very strong. The process of learning for a child is not magical. It is important that then student has should base of strong moral values.

So the student-teachers should develop the sensitivity of see when moral values are at stake and how meaning is giving to them. The student-teachers should incorporate this moral sensitivity in the art of their teaching. The above viewpoints have led to the investigation into the “A Study of Values among pupil teachers.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM : “A Study of Values among pupil teachers”.

Objectives

1. To find the significance of difference between values of male and female pupil teachers in respect of
 - (a) Theoretical value
 - (b) Economic value

- (c) Political value
- (d) Social value
- (e) Aesthetic value
- (f) Religious value

2. To find the significance of difference between values of arts and science pupil teachers in respect of

- (a) Theoretical value
- (b) Economic value
- (c) Political value
- (d) Social value
- (e) Aesthetic value
- (f) Religious value

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There is no significant difference between values of male and female pupil teachers in respect of

- (a) Theoretical value
- (b) Economic value
- (c) Political value
- (d) Social value
- (e) Aesthetic value
- (f) Religious value

2. There is no significant difference between values of arts and science pupil teachers in respect of

- (a) Theoretical value
- (b) Economic value
- (c) Political value
- (d) Social value
- (e) Aesthetic value
- (f) Religious value

Method Adopted for the Present Study

To investigate and to determine the status of present phenomenon the survey method is the best.

Population of the Study

“Population is a group of individual that have one or more characteristics in common, that are of interest of the research”. – **John. W. Best**

The population selected for this study was pupil teachers of Guru Nanak College of Education Dalewal, Hoshiarpur.

Sample of the study

In the present study, random sampling technique was adopted to select a sample of 250 Pupil teachers in Guru Nanak College of Education Dalewal, Hoshiarpur.

Tools used in the Study

The investigator used ‘Students Value Inventory’ which was developed and standardized by T.Padmanaban, for collecting data from Pupil teachers.

Statistical Techniques Used

Mean, Standard Deviation and ‘t’ test were the statistical techniques used.

DATA ANALYSIS

Hypothesis: 1

There is no significant difference between values of male and female Pupil teachers in respect of.

- (a) Theoretical value
- (b) Economic value
- (c) Political value
- (d) Social value
- (e) Aesthetic value
- (f) Religious value

VALUES	MALE N=115		FEMLAE N=135		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Theoretical value	18.46	4.76	19.96	4.44	2.56	S
Economic value	16.67	4.19	17.92	3.66	2.5	S
Political vale	12.29	3.28	13.74	3.08	3.59	S
Social value	13.76	4.68	15.24	3.75	2.74	S
Aesthetic value	8.69	2.11	9.31	1.93	2.42	S
Religious value	12.63	3.15	12.7	3.01	0.17	NS

Table-1

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between values of male and female Pupil teachers in respect of Religious value. But there is significant difference between values of male and female Pupil teachers in respect of Theoretical, Economic, Political, Social and Aesthetic values.

While comparing the mean scores of male and female Pupil teachers in respect of Theoretical, Economic, Political, Social and Aesthetic values, female student-teachers are better than male Pupil teachers.

Hypothesis : 2

There is no significant difference between values of arts and science B.Ed. student-teachers in respect of

- (a) Theoretical value.
- (b) Economic value.
- (c) Political value.
- (d) Social value
- (e) Aesthetic value.
- (f) Religious value.

Table-2

VALUES	ARTS STUDENTS N=73		SCIENCE STUDETNs N=177		Calculated ‘t’ value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Theoretical value	18.49	4.32	19.42	4.79	1.43	NS
Economic value	15.74	4.18	17.86	3.76	3.93	S
Political vale	12.33	3.16	13.21	3.28	1.96	S
Social value	14.52	4.69	14.41	4.19	0.19	NS
Aesthetic value	9.11	1.95	8.92	2.1	0.66	NS
Religious value	12.84	3.18	12.59	3.05	0.58	NS

(At 5% level of Significance, the table value of ‘t’ is 1.96)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between values of arts and science Pupil teachers in respect of Theoretical, Social, Aesthetic and Religious value. But there is significant difference between values of arts and science Pupil teachers in respect of Economic and Political values.

While comparing the mean scores of arts and science Pupil teachers in respect of Economic and Political values, science student-teachers are better than arts student-teachers.

CONCLUSION

Students are foundation stone in development of any nation. Teachers shape personality of their students. Ordinary teachers can bring about extraordinary transformation in the society. A teacher should practice what he preaches. Teachers are a role model of students. their actions convey more than their words. Students learn values from what the teachers are rather than from what they say. Teacher makes a maximum impact on the personality of a student in the formative years. Students imbibe virtues and vices knowingly and unknowingly from theses role models. Teachers demonstrate the appropriate behavior of their students by their actions .

So the student-teachers must have healthy attitude and should possess rich values. Teaching is all about attitude positive/negative towards their job of imparting quality education. Teacher should act as a friend, philosopher and guide. A teacher is not only a source of information but is also a mentor and guardian. For this the studen –teachers must respect the teaching profession, love her subjects and students and possess values like kindness, honesty, compassion, righteousness, peace, love, non-violence and high self-esteem.

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The most important agent for building the character of the student is a teacher. Swami Vivekananda says that "character is nothing but a bundle of habits formed through repeated acts. Character building can change the nation as strong foundation is required for a strong building, strong character is required for nation–building.